
An Analysis of Theories of Career Development

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Abstract:

The purpose of the article is to carry out an in-depth analysis of career development theories and to know the practical implications in modern organizations. Content analysis method has been implemented for studying published literature on career theories. The outcome of the study shows that no single theory can be applicable to all situations and necessitates a combination of approach. Moreover, the factors emphasized by different theories that regulate a person changes very often with the changing organizational contours in this volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity (VUCA) world. As a result, the organizations need to adapt with the changing scenario with an appropriate modified model to reap the benefit of career development. The study is limited to only five career development theories and the theories are analysed on the evidences collected from secondary sources. This study provides an insight into the changing professional world with individual coping strategies to the volatile work environment. It prescribes a path towards occupational growth and professional wellbeing for an individual. It also attempts to provide systematic steps to create a platform for career development of employees.

Keywords: Career Development, Process Theories, Content Theories

Introduction:

Career development theories show the various paths towards improving professional growth and the career trajectory followed by individuals for an overall job satisfaction and goal achievement. Understanding these theories is an essential step in determining the strengths, weaknesses, fundamental values, and desirable path that are operative while choosing a career. There are various types of career development theories that focus on different factors, and quite dissimilar to one another. Still all the theories recognise the importance of cultivating a positive emotional relation with work or work environment for developing and achieving a meaningful professional goal. Career development theories can be divided into four categories: by using trait factor, a proper match between individual traits to

occupations is focused upon (like trait and factor theory by Frank Parson); it can be based on psychological structure, where the personality should correspond with the work environment (like Holland theory); it can be grounded on decision - situational factors (like social cognitive career theory); and it can be constructed on self-concept (like life span theory of Super). Besides this categorisation, another type of division can be noticed in the theories that are: process theories, content theories, and process-content theories. The process theories emphasise on communicating about the interaction and changes that occurs over a period of time. These theories deal with a sequence of stages through which people proceeds (example: Super's life-span, life-space approach to career development, Gottfredson's circumscription and compromise theory). The content theories

are connected with the features of an individual and the environment they live in. The impact on career development are thought to be either intrinsic to the individual or it is initiated from the context or surrounding in which they live. For example: Theory of Work Adjustment. The content and process theories have been moulded in response to accommodate with the requirements of process theory and content theory. These theories embrace both the characteristics of context and individuals, and the advancement and dealings between them (example: Krumboltz's social learning theory of career decision-making, social cognitive career theory, Roe's theory of personality development and career choice).

Objectives and Methodology of the Study:

The study is carried out to gain knowledge about the philosophy and theoretical underpinnings behind career development. Effort is also made to identify the various empirical research conducted by using these theories. As intrinsic as well as extrinsic factors impact career development, attention is provided to understand the same from existing literature. Finally attempt is made to understand the career path or stages adopted by the theories. Content analysis method has been implemented for studying published literature on career theories.

Content Theories:

(a) Theory of Work Adjustment or Person-Environment Correspondence Theory:

The Theory of Work Adjustment (TWA) is based on the difference of individuals and vocational behaviour (Dawis, 2002, 2005; Dawis & Lofquist, 1984). It views career choice as an unbroken process consisting of adjustment and accommodation. The theory declares two processes that an individual adheres to. In the first case, an individual or person (P) searches for a work environment (E) that can

match with his requirement. In the second phase E searches for P having the skills that can tally with the needs of the organization. The amount of satisfaction of P depends on his needs and satisfactoriness of E is based on the operational skills of P helps to forecast the tenure of P. There are four types of adjustment maintained by person and environment (Dawis, 2005). The first one is flexibility that denotes to a person level of tolerance in environment. Next is activeness where P tries to modify E. The third is reactivity where P adopts a self-modification to the difficult situation without transforming E. The fourth is perseverance in which P determines to adjust before choosing to leave E.

(b) Holland's Theory of Vocational Personalities in Work Environment:

The theory of Holland can be applied in career counselling and career guidance. Holland expressed that vocational interest and personality is organised in hexagonal structure in the order of RIASEC and can be codified into Realistic (R), Investigative (I), Artistic (A), Social (S), Enterprising (E), and Conventional (C). Generally, this six types of interest and personality can take two type of forms by producing three-letter code e.g., RIA, SIA that symbolizes one's career interest. The first letter of these two codes shows the chief interest of the person and the second and third alphabets denotes significant but secondary interest in the course of career choice. Holland used the word "congruence" to show the person-environment interaction where the personality and interest of the person and the work environment produces vocational stability and satisfaction and a low congruence causes vocational instability and dissatisfaction.

Process Theories:

(a) Self-concept Theory of Career Development:

Among various theories of career development, the theory given by Super has received abundant attention in USA and other nations. Super established that career development and career choice is related with the self-concept of the person. A self-concept is a complex dealing among the mental and physical growth, environmental features, personal experience etc. (Super, 1990).

(b) Gottfredson's Theory of Circumscription and Compromise:

Gottfredson's theory of career development is a new input in the theory of career development. Gottfredson (1981,1996, 2002, 2005) supposed that the process of career choice demands for a greater level of cognitive ability. Gottfredson's (2002, 2005) expounded on the interplay between the concept of genetic makeup and environment. The theory have got little attention as it is problematic to test it empirically Swanson and Gore (2000) because (a) its variables like prestige, circumscription, compromise, sex type are tough to implement (b) the developmental process is suitable for longitudinal studies which requires ample time. But still the theory can be used for career guidance like gender stereotype found in the cultures of Asia, where a person chooses a profession which he consider suitable for his gender (Leung, 2002)

Analysis of the theories:

The theories of career development served a prominent role by encouraging research activity. By analysing the abovementioned theories of career development, it is found that most of them are related to the career behaviour of an individual. The theories are mostly descriptive in nature rather than explanatory even though they are tested by several researchers. Some theories has been applied much more (e.g. super theory of self-concept) as compared with other theories

have got a mixed result (e.g. Holland theory). There exist some contrasting factors among the theories.

Holland's theory (1959) identifies the factors that trigger the vocational behaviour of a person while other theories deal with the purpose and development of vocational behaviours. Trait factors associated with Holland's theory explains very little about vocational behaviour. This theory is also having certain limitations. The theory needs to settle up the inconsistencies of personality required for a proper operation in an occupation. The concept of role identification in career development has been approved by empirical evidences whereas the idea of psychic energy for vocational activity has acquired little support. A substantial amount of research on Super's theory has provided experimental confirmation of self-concept and career development task that is identified with a specific vocational decision.

Findings:

- The theories generally focus on individual, environment and interrelation between the two.
- The study of theories shows that no particular theory can be suitable for every situation and every person.
- One type of theory cannot be applicable to all types of individuals or environment.
- A particular theory may not be applicable in long run. When the needs of a person changes or the requirement of an organization changes then the theory lacks its ability to influence.

Conclusion:

By studying the above mentioned career related theories, we can find that these theories discourses about the career related outcome (Chen, 2001; Dik, Duffy, &

Eldridge, 2009). The study gives a detail vision into the various factors like personality, professional growth, self-concept, social situation etc. that sometimes performs as a source of encouragement and other time acts as barriers for an individual while choosing a career. The varied perspectives of career development theories offer valuable evidence that reflects employee development. These theories help to acquire knowledge about the ways by which an individual develops his career remaining in an organization and the methods that an individual adopts to adjust and achieves knowledge and skills accordance with various circumstances, needs, and social situations. It is suggested that while implementing a theory an organization should know about its employees' needs and should consider on the practicability of applying the theory. This study complements with Super (1992) who advised that no single theory is sufficient enough to show the career progress of a person, rather each theory advocates certain idea and neglects the other part of individual career choice (Krumboltz, 1994). This study concludes that one particular theory may be operative for a person in a particular time but may be dysfunctional during other time.

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